
NEGOTIATING URBAN SPACE FOR EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN MICRO-ENTREPRENEURS IN KAMPALA CENTRAL DIVISION, UGANDA.

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ABSTRACT

This study examined how women micro entrepreneurs negotiated and used the patriarchal urban space in Kampala Central Division for empowerment.

The study utilised Lefebvre's spatial triad model of space theory and the Empowerment theory. The study employed a cross-sectional study design that allowed the use of the survey and case study designs with several research methods that included questionnaire, observation, key informant interviews, literature review discussions, and cases. Key information was collected from five Kampala Capital City Authority (KCCA) officials and five local council leaders, who were purposively selected and 90 women entrepreneurs that participated in a survey through purposive and snowball sampling.

The study discovered that, women Kampala Central Division offers space for women's micro-entrepreneurship that has brought remarkable decision making processes, resilience and improved agency which are aspects of empowerment. The study also discovered flaws and challenges that limited women from accessing the urban space to sell their items, which affected the empowerment process. The women cited limited start-up capital, high operational dues, stiff competition from other traders, difficulty in accessing the patriarchal urban space and increase in women's workload which reduced productivity, among other challenges. In light of the above findings, it is therefore recommended that KCCA should address the apparent challenges and flaws to mitigate the negative impact of such deficiencies in their performance and uptake by the women micro entrepreneurs in Kampala Central Division.

Keywords: Urbanization, empowerment, agency, microenterprise, patriarchy, spatial

INTRODUCTION

Uganda's national unemployment rate is 9.2%, while the unemployment rate for youth aged 18-30 is 13.3% (UBOS, 2021). This condition has forced many vulnerable communities into micro businesses composed of 50.2% male and 49.8% female business enterprises that are characterised by the sale of food at roadside stalls, traders' markets, and verandas hawking clothes and food stuffs from place to place, while others brew and sell alcohol (UNDP, 2019). This is a clear testimony that if self-employment is improved, unemployment and poverty will reduce (Esaku, 2021).

To that end, the urban population in Kampala, has almost doubled from 1.94 million in 2010 to 3.14 in 2019, 3.30 in 2020, a 5.22 percentage growth rate from 2019 (UBOS, 2019). The women micro entrepreneurs in Kampala participate in trading and services which operate in traders' markets, homes, small rented rooms, semi-permanent wooden structures, roadside booths, hawking from one place to another and street vending, to mention but a few (Bidandi., 2015). Moreover, many women micro entrepreneurs are operating from their homes or non-permanent premises, which are not covered by the Census of Business Establishments (Bidandi & Williams, 2017).

Therefore, urban space is not an infinite entity, but is rather contested between different individuals, groups, and entities for ownership and/or use (Fuchs, 2018c). However, lack of proper planning for the urban population growth and limited working space mean that most of the urban poor especially women, live in appalling conditions (The World Bank, 2019). This condition can curtail the growth of women enterprises and transformation of gender power relations, agency, and gender equality which ultimately affects the empowerment process for urban women micro entrepreneurs in one way or the other (Bressan et al., 2023). To that effect, most small businesses in Uganda fail within their early stages of operation mainly due to limited working space, under-capitalization and / or lack of proper management and business skills (The World Bank, 2019).

Moreover, it is not clear how urban women negotiate their time use both at home and in urban places. What is required is to find ways of empowering women to earn a good return from their investments, be able to make decisions and operate sustainable formal business ventures. The empowerment also should extend to women negotiating with patriarchal husbands who deter them from going to the public sphere and ownership of factors of production. This therefore underscores the need to better understand how urban women micro entrepreneurs are coping as regards empowerment in emerging economies like Uganda, using Kampala as a case study.

It is also believed that urbanisation provides space for women to make choices, and action, influence women's micro enterprises, increase women's agency and empower them. Uganda's National Development Plan III (NDP III, 2020/2021-2024/25) and Vision 2040 prioritize the empowerment of women and gender equality as a means to inclusive growth and social development (Republic of Uganda, 2021). This agenda aims to increase household incomes and improve the quality of life of Ugandans through sustainable industrialisation for inclusive growth, employment and sustainable wealth creation. This is line with sustainable development goal (SDG) 8.3b which aimed at promoting development-oriented policies that support productive activities, decent job creation, entrepreneurship, creativity and innovation, and encouraging the formalization and growth of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises, including through access to financial services (UN, 2015). This study, thus looks at how

women micro entrepreneurs access and use Kampala urban spaces and most importantly, restrict and mould these spaces for their own use in a bid to get empowered.

METHODOLOGY

Using a cross-sectional design, the study was carried out in Kampala district which is found in Central Uganda. Data was collected through qualitative interviews that such as observation, key informant interviews, literature review discussions, and cases and quantitative survey using a questionnaire. Key information was collected from Kampala Capital City Authority (KCCA) documents through documentary review, and five women leaders, who were purposively selected and 90 women entrepreneurs that participated in a survey through purposive and snowball sampling. The study adopted a quantitative method, which offered a more detailed understanding of the experiences of women micro entrepreneurs. The data collected were analyzed quantitatively for in-depth understanding of how access and use of urban spaces by women micro-entrepreneurs empowered or did not empower women.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

This paper sought to examine the way women micro entrepreneurs negotiated their way into the urban spaces for micro entrepreneurship, the places where they live and how they obtained working capital for their small businesses in a bid to get empowered.

Women's negotiation and use of the urban space in Kampala Central Division for micro entrepreneurship.

In this theme, we present how women negotiated their way into the highly patriarchal urban space, their working capital and how they access credit/start-up capital for their own business.

Women's negotiation and use of the urban space in Kampala Central Division for micro entrepreneurship.

From the findings, vendors tended to locate their enterprises on roads and paths with high human traffic that offers a market for their goods such as socks, knickers, fruits, tomatoes, oranges, onions, yellow bananas at roadside stalls, traders' markets, and verandas, hawking clothes and food stuffs from one place to another.

A few shop attendants and building owners allowed micro entrepreneurs on the pavements in front of their shops for a fee. However, even among those who paid for spaces, 50% did not occupy the spaces permanently. They still shifted to other spaces depending on the terms of payments with space 'owners' and law enforcement conditions. Yet, about 3.3% of micro entrepreneurs obtained permission from KCCA to carry out their activities. A study made in Kampala noted that "vendors had been allocated vending sites outside the central business district (CBD) that they had rejected, arguing that they were inaccessible to customers" (Gumisiriza, 2021).

Starting a business symbolized independence. For rural to urban migrants, Kampala offered self-sufficiency, a metropolitan lifestyle, a chance to escape family-imposed gender norms (predominantly for older women) and the realisation of dreams and aspirations (in the case of younger women). Most of the women were passionately in love with Kampala, a great town with good people, weather, location, urban expansion, and business opportunities. One woman said: 'When I came from the village I decided to work, it is better to live here in town

with electricity than being rich in a village' (Said a 44 year, divorced with three children, one grandchild, and a migrant). Another woman commented, pointing at the freedom that Kampala city gave to her intimate life: 'I like it (Kampala) very much! No matter whether you have something to eat or not, to feel comfortable and have a good sleep [meaning not having a person you do not like in your bed] is great' (Said a 20 year, hair salon, divorced, childless, and migrant).

Yet, similar allocations are still being done that compel vendors to return to their preferred but outlawed places. This is because, the location of goods on a particular street varies, and "the value of street vending lies in its ability to generate economic opportunities for a sizeable number of residents and help them to escape extreme poverty"(Ismail, 2020). This is in line with Kabeer's (2017) assertion on empowerment that such an act enables the actors to represent their interests in a responsible and self-determined way, acting on their own authority.

On average, getting space in which to operate from, in the survey area, was not easy. This was because, the majority of the respondents (62.14%) found it difficult to get working space. Besides, when space was got, the working conditions were not conducive due to gruesome acts of enforcement officers (KCCA). Pictures of women carrying babies on their backs and baskets of mangoes on the head running away from law enforcement officers is not what the government wants appearing on different media platforms. Sadly so, a 38-year-old Olivia Basemera, a single mother who was vending handkerchiefs—died while running from KCCA enforcement officers. The rebelliousness of street vendors can be equated to the works of Lefebvre (1996), who promoted the notion of the right to the city. He saw "right to the city as a struggle to "de-alienate" urban space, to reintegrate it into the web of social connections. However, the spontaneous location of street enterprises may continue not only because it is an unemployment alternative but it has been part of our culture stemming from the perception that streets provide opportunities for social interactions with a potential for economic gains.

Notably some women micro entrepreneurs acquired street space through social capital. The women had acquired the space, through talking to the management of the respective place while others were connected by friends, while others observed that they obtained the spaces through talking to security guards who permitted the women to sell from the street. Other vendors obtained the street spaces from their relatives; who had secured the space for them.

On the other hand, the criminalisation of micro entrepreneurs has had a significant impact on the livelihood strategies of a large segment of the urban poor in Kampala. Micro entrepreneurs commonly face food insecurity and limited access to housing, and many live in the slums that house approximately 85% of the city's poor population or simply sleep on the streets. By deploying its enforcement officers, over the last seven years, KCCA has been arresting and prosecuting street vendors impounding their small business items as well as constantly surveilling the streets. These actions have left a considerable number of informal micro entrepreneurs disempowered, a majority of them being women. These acts coupled with limited space available to them to freely conduct their activities impede the growth of women enterprises as well as the transformation of gender power relations, agency, and gender equality (Basemera, 2021).

According to the survey, securing a street space was another hustle in Kampala central. Mary, a snacks vendor on Luwum Street, exclaims,

"It is not easy to acquire a permanent street space for vending on the streets of Kampala city if not connected by someone who has a big say in a given place. Tracing it on your own can take time and encountering challenges with the space owners and fellow vendors who acquired the space sometime back."

Some areas have got caretakers to watch over them. These require a vendor to go through the proper application procedures to start vending.

Similarly, Moser (2021) suggests that paradigmatic case studies describe the general characteristics of the societies in question. In this case, residents of Kampala city have tended to be more responsive to roadside enterprises due to their convenience during shopping than businesses located inside buildings.

Poor government service provision means that the women also need to pay for things that might, under different circumstances, be free or more affordable, including transportation, healthcare and education. School fees, which are charged for all levels of education, are a particular burden for micro entrepreneurs, many of whom are single parents, as the inability to pay can perpetuate extreme poverty by forcing children to leave school, after which they commonly enter the informal sphere due to a lack of alternative means of livelihood support. This is in line with Kuch's (2018c) argument that those in power, together with those in collusion with governmental agencies, impose spatial constraints that regiment the lived experience of entire populations.

The repression of micro entrepreneurs has been particularly harsh given the role of the state in producing and sustaining informal economic activity through poor economic management. Besides, the exacerbating geographic developmental divisions, greatly contributed to the conditions that allow urban informality to flourish. This fact has not been lost on many who have criticised the KCCA for its treatment of micro entrepreneurs. Nonetheless, Gumisirisa's (2020), study has castigated the government for adopting 'draconian' policies as a substitute for its failure to aid the country's manufacturing and agricultural industries as well as the unemployed, and says that micro entrepreneurs 'have nowhere to go' because the government 'has not developed alternatives'. 'The reason they do their business is a breakdown of economic policy.' This implies that, the ban 'is not really about street vending', but rather the fact that the government 'has no real policy to help the urban poor'.

How micro-entrepreneurs retained their working spaces

Most women had to be physically present every day so that their spaces were not taken up. Some of the responses concerning daily practice included, "I do the business every day," others replied, "I make sure I have stock every day," others said, "we use the same space to work in shifts." However, there were conditions for the use of street space; for example, some said, "I ensure that the place is clean daily," another said that "I do not make noise here." In addition, some keep space "through perseverance" such that "when KCCA comes, I run away" and that "when KCCA confiscates my stock, I look for more capital."

Thus, even when the choice of location was spontaneous, managing one's space mattered, especially concerning keeping a good reputation with neighbours, paying their dues, and having a daily occupation of the space. Besides occupying space, it mattered how the space was retained. Subsequently, 27.8% of respondents mentioned that social capital was why they could retain their street spaces. Some of the responses to social capital included; "I cooperate

with my neighbours," "my friend helps me to secure the place," "I pay the security guard," "I am a friend to the manager,"

"I befriended the vendors that I found here," "we work cooperatively as vendors." Similarly, vendors who kept their street space were perceived as "trustworthy, have discipline, good conduct and maintained good relationships." Hence aside from spontaneous allocation of enterprises, social capital through various forms of proper conduct re-enforced their ability to keep their spaces. Yet when 19% of respondents said they were allocated the space they currently occupy, they retained them; the question was how they maintained it. Specific responses included "I pay rent in time," "once you get a place here, it becomes yours for good until you give it out," "I pay something daily," "I always pay taxes." Hence monetary forms of exchange for space were cited.

Meanwhile, 16.7% of respondents paid rent directly to space owners of the vendors who were allocated spaces. The payment arrangements were in cash and kind, exchange of goods and services, and acts of reciprocity with space owners. However, one of the factors to retain acquired street space was the availability of the market, which accounted for 13.3% of respondents. The market was both a motivating factor and a force that drew them to the spaces. Selected responses include; "I bring good products that customers want," "I sell at cheaper prices," "I have original products," "everyone on the street knows that this place is for beads," "I know what my customers want," "I serve my customers well," and "I sell fresh goods." These statements are in line with a study by Bressan et al., (2023) who has argued that in just one generation some aspects of intra-household gender equity have improved dramatically in Uganda, such as further domination in decision-making in the natal household. How they negotiated their pathways to independence through different spaces is of particular interest in this paper.

In this study, vendors targeted a specific market in their areas of operation. Hence, a relationship was formed between vendors and buyers. Considering that even when the market was one of the reasons to retain street space, social capital was the main force that protected an individual from losing their spaces. The bonds that vendors create on the street enable them to protect and defend one another. It was noted in a similar context that "The other aspects of their social network include trust among particular sub-groups, habitual exchanges of favours, and mutual support among the vendors and their friends" (Gumisiriza, 2021).

Areas of operation by micro-entrepreneurs

As far as the business areas were concerned, Kafumbe Mukasa road (behind Owino market) accounted for the biggest number of respondents, that is 39 (27.9%) out of the total 140. The main reason was that, Kafumbe Mukasa compared to the other areas of survey (Nakivubo Mews, Nakasero/Market Street, Kafumbe Mukasa and Kisenyi) had more micro entrepreneurs. Nakasero/Market Street, which makes up a considerable portion of Kampala Central Division and is, with major government buildings and the city's Central Business District, the city's political and economic centre, and Kisenyi, an adjacent built-up area to the southwest of Nakasero. Both are prime areas for micro-entrepreneurs in Kampala. The other reason was that the micro enterprise women respondents in this area (Kafumbe Mukasa) were not so brutalised or manhandled by the KCCA enforcement officers, as was the case with their (women micro entrepreneurs) counterparts in other areas. Kafumbe Mukasa road was somehow gazetted by the KCCA authorities, and hence, selling on the roadside was not so much controlled as was the case with the other survey areas.

Transport system and the road network.

An effective, affordable, and inclusive transport system is the engine for the development of any city (The World Bank, 2020). However, despite the efforts taken up by the government of Uganda and Kampala Capital City Authority to ensure their improvement, the existing tarmacked roads have potholes and most roads within the city are inaccessible when it rains, or very dusty during the dry seasons. The situation with the transport system has not only contributed to wastage of time due to traffic jams, but also negatively affected business growth as it makes it hard for some women to access or be exposed to potential markets, and it increases the cost of doing business in the city.

Whereas 50 percent of the women's homes were located about ten kilometres from the city centre, the cost of transport was a significant barrier to market access. On the other hand, some women who did not live far or lived within the central business, preferred walking from their areas of operation to their homes and vice versa. By avoiding the use of taxis, the women attested to saving the little earnings from their businesses. Thirdly and relatedly, there was a significant acute shortage of commercial space in the city. This finding confirms what Were et al's (2022) study says that, women thus experience a historic difficulty in their relationship with the city and within urban spaces.

Provision of shelter and basic service

In order to circumvent masculine power and patriarchy in the urban space, findings show that 47 percent of the women entrepreneurs adapt to the prevailing circumstances by depending on relatives, and friends to settle. Notably a number of micro entrepreneurs were provided with food and shelter by extended family on arrival in Kampala city. Those without direct family connections were able to draw upon support of friends or relatives. Depending on prior experience, new arrivals were able to find jobs and apprenticeships in transport, restaurants and people's homes before their own enterprises within a walkable distance from their respective workplaces. Nonetheless, there were barriers to accessing the streets (space) where market was readily available. This condition can curtail the growth of women enterprises and transformation of gender power relations, agency, and gender equality which ultimately affects the empowerment process for urban women micro entrepreneurs in one way or the other (Bidandi and Williams, 2017).

Obtaining working capital for business

Figure 2.1: Sources of funds to sustain the business

From the study findings, 45 percent of the urban women micro entrepreneurs obtained start-up capital after saving in small-scale jobs such as house maids, food vending while 20 percent borrowed from family members. Others attested to have borrowed from the savings schemes of the groups that they had earlier joined. Women micro entrepreneurs that had no access to capital instead borrowed goods from Kikuubo and Nakasero Market Street traders (agency), which were the centres of goods for wholesale trade. The women sold these items such as food items (these included beans, peas, carrots, yellow bananas), knickers, socks, from small spaces such as corridors and verandas of big shops, others displayed their goods on pieces of clothes alongside the streets, while others hawk their goods from one shop to another, from one vehicle to another and from one street to another in pursuit of pedestrians (buyers).

Other micro entrepreneurs received credit from suppliers, which credit they paid back, noting that “they got money after selling their products.” This contradicts the argument by Bullough et al, (2022) that norms limit women’s ability to bargain for official credit. This means that the use of the urban space increases the ability of the microentrepreneurs to make independent entrepreneurial credit decisions within the household. This cuts the husband out as a centre of power and increases the influence of the woman over the decisions about entrepreneurial credit.

This finding shows how women negotiated their way to obtain working capital in terms of goods that they would later sell to eke a living. This in line with Esaku’s (2021) study findings that alludes that, with that effect therefore, the physical properties of space influence how people experience it but only in conjunction with people’s perception of the space.

Acts of discrimination, patriarchy and sexual exploitation

More micro entrepreneurs reported being victims of discrimination and sexual harassment by both male counterparts and prospective customers, who called the women ‘prostitutes’. Another participant expressed the desire to be treated like a human being in Kampala rather than a victim on the streets. This corroborates the earlier findings by Moser’s (2020), assertion that women become victims of urban discrimination, since their exclusion from the gendered

space of the city, where they are allowed only as graceful decorations, force them into a form of aphasia. Such types of gender-related discrimination are often occasioned by socio-cultural factors which pose hindrances to women's entrepreneurial activity thus affecting the empowerment process (Were et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, some women asserted that the small businesses were not sufficient enough to take care of their family needs such as food, rent, and school fees for their children, and other related school costs. As such they resorted to sex 'for survival' as a way of making ends meet. To that end, such women realize that their lack of status and welfare, relative to men is not due to their lack of ability, organization or effort. This finding corroborates Kabeer's (2017) who refers to such tendencies as the emotional state of disempowerment that involves lack of realization of their relative capacity arising from discriminatory practices, patriarchal tendencies and rules which give priority access to men. Similarly, Bullough (2022) writes, women's relationship to the city is conditioned in three ways, as they are seen as an object of desire, a body for sale and a form of public exhibition.

Conclusion

International and national policies have prioritised the empowerment of women and gender equality as a means to inclusive growth and social development. This agenda aims to increase household incomes and improve the quality of life of Ugandans through sustainable development-oriented policies that support productive activities, decent job creation, entrepreneurship, creativity and innovation, and encouraging the formalization and growth of micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises, including through access to financial service. This study, thus looked at how women micro entrepreneurs accessed and used Kampala urban spaces and most importantly, restrict and mould these spaces for their own use in a bid to get empowered. To that end therefore, the study concludes as follows;

Women's negotiation and use of the urban space in Kampala Central Division for micro entrepreneurship

- Women entrepreneurs in Kampala Central division develop their small informal businesses through the spaces of marginality and the articulation of independence which is an indicator of empowerment. Space is mutually constitutive with gender and place and integral to time. It 'is by its very nature of power and symbolism, a complex web of the relation of domination and subordination, of solidarity and co-operation'.
- Women's access and usage of the urban space for micro entrepreneurship has led to independence, decision making as well as improved agency which attributes were gained through mobility and developing women's income source and is seen as control over their businesses and bodies.
- Space and place have been originally considered as arenas in which social life unfolds, later 'as a medium through which gender social life is produced and reproduced' and subjectivities are formed. The lens of negotiating 'independence' integrates spaces of conflicting subjectivities.
- Marginality of women micro entrepreneurs as well as resistance, suffering and claimed control, interpellation, and re-construction of own identities were simultaneously present in the urban spaces of Kampala.

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